

INTERNATIONAL
ASTRONOMICAL
UNION | OFFICE OF
ASTRONOMY FOR
DEVELOPMENT

TARGET GROUPS

INDIVIDUALS

Inhabitants of rural, socioeconomically underdeveloped areas.

Their strengths are that they generally live in areas with abundant, free dark skies, and possess distinct cultural elements like food, rituals, and way of life.

BUSINESSES

Existing tourism businesses who want to implement astrotourism.

Their strengths are existing tourism skills, infrastructure, and established logistical elements of experience.

ORGANISATIONS

Observatories who can help surrounding rural inhabitants create experiences.

Their strengths are the ability to provide extended support to rural inhabitants to help them create a night sky experience.

Common Challenge

A lack of knowledge, clarity or knowing where to start with astrotourism

THE APPROACH: Instead of focusing on target group weaknesses, we want to empower them to use their strengths for astrotourism.

The approach to this is to disentangle astrotourism from science-based, niche tourism and engage with astronomy and the night sky from ecotourism and cultural tourism perspectives, harnessing existing ecological and cultural resources. In a practical sense, this looks like making astrotourism easier to implement by broadening the scope of astrotourism activities from things that focus on the night sky (e.g. telescope tours) to easy-to-implement activities that also allow the night sky or night sky elements as a backdrop for activities (e.g. dinner under the stars).

FLAGSHIP 1 RESOURCES OVERVIEW

INDIVIDUALS

Night Sky Tourism: A Quick Start Guide

A short crash course into creating a tourism product for rural areas. Visual emphasis and designed for affordable printing.

Night Sky Tourism: Workbook

Quick start guide in a guided interactive format.

BUSINESSES

A Night Sky Tourism Guide for Tourism Businesses

A guide to bridge the transition into astrotourism by providing practical insights and step-by-step instructions for integrating night sky experiences into existing tourism offerings.

ORGANISATIONS

Night Sky Tourism for Communities around Observatories

A guide to curating a variety of complementary activities during observatory downtime, integrating astronomy to generate additional revenue for local communities.

WEBPAGE
WITH MORE
INFORMATION
AND LINKS TO
RESOURCES

For more information and resources visit
astrotourism.astro4dev.org, or
email
astrotourism@astro4dev.org

IF YOU ARE
RUNNING AN
ASTRO-
TOURISM
PROJECT:

